

Kinetics of the Reaction between Sulphuric Acid and the Water-decomposition Product of Blue Peroxychromic Acid Extracted with Ethyl Acetate

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We have already shown¹ that when the blue peroxychromic acid is extracted with ethyl acetate, its water-decomposition product is $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_8)_3$ with chromium present in it in hexavalent and trivalent states. In analogy with potassium dipersulphate, it has been named as chromium diperchromate. In the present communication, the nature of this compound has further been investigated.

The blue peroxychromic acid was prepared and isolated in the same manner, described in an earlier communication¹. This was carefully separated and washed with ice-cold distilled water. The blue solution was separated finally, taken into a Jena glass bottle, and kept in ice. The blue acid (50 ml) was withdrawn into a flask containing distilled water (100ml) and left for decomposition. When the decomposition was complete and the ethyl acetate layer became colorless, the aqueous layer was separated carefully for the kinetic study.

Two flasks were taken containing 50 ml each of water-decomposition product and $2N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$, respectively. These flasks were kept in a thermostat maintained at a desired temperature. After about 15 min. the contents of the flasks were mixed, the stop-watch started, and 10-ml portion of the reaction mixture was withdrawn immediately into a titration flask containing aqueous potassium iodide solution. Liberated iodine was titrated against a standard sodium thiosulphate solution. This provided the initial concentration of the water-decomposition product in terms of the volume of sodium thiosulphate solution consumed. Similar titrations were performed after every 10 min. or so. The infinite reading was taken after the expiry of 24 hr. It was found that after 24 hr. the colour of the reaction mixture was the characteristic green and it did not liberate iodine any more, *i.e.*, infinite reading was zero. The above experiment was repeated at two other temperatures.

As the reaction between water-decomposition product, *i.e.*, $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_8)_3$, and H_2SO_4 proceeded, the capacity of the former to liberate iodine gradually decreased in all cases and in the end no iodine was liberated. The end product, having a characteristic green colour was $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$. This shows that the water-decomposition product is completely reduced to a trivalent state in acidic medium. This also indicates that the acid reacts with the water-decomposition product, generating hydrogen peroxide which, in turn, in presence of

acid reduces the water-decomposition product to $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$. The reaction may be represented as:

If the values of $\log(a-x)$ are plotted against t , the data fall very close on a straight line in accordance with the requirement of a first-order reaction (Fig. 1). The average values of the rate constants are 0.00571, 0.0196, and 0.0576 at 20° , 30° , and 40° respectively. From these (on the basis of the Arrhenius equation), the average value of the energy of activation comes out to be 20.2 kcal.

FIG. 1 Mono-order reaction between H_2SO_4 and $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3$.

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